

Groups and Geometries. Lino di Martino, William M. Kantor, Guglielmo Lunardon, Antonia Pasini and Maria Clara Tamburini, eds. Sienna Conference. Birkhauser. 1996.

This book is the proceedings of a conference on 'Groups and Geometries' at Sienna, Italy, September 1996. As the title indicates, the topics covered in the book deal mainly with the interplay between groups and geometries. In detail, they deal with:

1. Classification of finite simple groups (e.g. M. Aschbacher's article gives an exposé of work on the classification of quasi-thin groups, Baumeister's article is on a new proof of existence of one of Janko's simple groups).
2. Buildings and geometry of projective and polar spaces (e.g. A. Brouwer: Geometry away from a point or a chamber, E. Shult etc.).
3. Geometry of sporadic simple groups.

The classification theorems of finite simple groups are notoriously difficult and involved. It is desirable to have simple conceptual proofs in the theory whenever possible. It is noteworthy that this book studies many of the simple groups via properties of their action on geometric objects. The book will be a welcome addition to the library of anyone who is interested in the study of finite groups.

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Annual Review of Nuclear and Particle Science 1997. Chris Quigg, ed. Annual Reviews Inc., 4139 El Camino Way, Palo Alto CA94303-0139, USA. vol. 47. 721 pp. Price: Individuals US \$75; Institutions US \$150.

This is yet another excellent volume in this well-known series. As usual there is a wide coverage of several areas by experts. There is a wealth of interesting and useful information here. In the remi-

niscences of Jack Steinberger, we learn that Fermi did not believe in universality of weak interactions. This reflects Fermi's open mind, considering the fact that Fermi's theory of nuclear beta decay was a truly path-breaking development in quantum field theory which brought order in understanding a vast array of experimental data in terms of one coupling constant.

High energy physicists can be truly proud of their invention of the world wide web which has revolutionized communications in the world at large. The article by Bebo White gives an excellent account of the 'history' of this activity, current status and future possibilities. Among the latter are electronic journals, active objects and laboratories.

With advances in modern technology we can now build accelerators with better stability properties and higher luminosities. Himel describes lucidly the feedback principles while Zisman examines the challenges involved in increasing luminosity by a factor of hundred.

The last few years have witnessed advances in atom cooling techniques which have led to demonstrating Bose-Einstein condensation with alkali atoms. Laser trapping methods are described by Sprouse and Orozco.

After the so-called proton spin crisis, no longer does one say that spin is an inessential complication. Spin polarized targets are the concern of the review by Crabb and Meyer. Mass measurements of nuclei far from stability like ^9He , ^{14}Be and ^{16}B are described by Mittag *et al.* Light ion storage rings have opened a novel area in nuclear physics that has much in common with particle physics is what we learn from the article by Meyer.

Gamma ray bursters promise to reveal something about the early universe. A new generation of Cerenkov telescopes can provide us much insight into a number of fundamental problems in astrophysics and cosmology is the theme of Aharaonian and Akerlof's article. Ricci and Brillat review the gravitational wave detectors which will be in the forefront of research in the coming decades.

There are many excellent articles on aspects of QCD by well-known experts. These include Hadronic form factors, Instanton model of the vacuum, heavy quark theory, hadrons in the nuclear medium. Practitioners of lattice QCD as

well as nuclear physicists will enjoy reading the article on Monte Carlo simulations in Shell model studies.

Heavy ion collisions will be a major theme of research in the coming decade. Systematic description of collective flow involving large number of nucleons can be found in the review by Reisdorf and Ritter.

All in all this is an excellent volume which every nuclear and particle physicist will find worthwhile to possess.

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Internet Industry Almanac. Egil Juliussen and Karen Petska-Juliussen. Computer Industry Almanac Inc., <http://www.c-i-a.com>. March 1998. 390 pp.

The internet industry is perhaps the fastest growing industry today. For twenty years, from 1969 to 1989, ARPANET and its successor, the internet, remained virtually obscure, known only to a few academics and government researchers in the United States. Certain events in 1989 led to the opening up of the internet and within five years the internet had surpassed the PC industry as the most important segment of the computer industry. Today, the internet has a profound impact on the entire gamut of information and communication industries such as telecommunication, computer electronics, broadcasting, publishing, financial services, entertainment, advertising and electronic commerce. Thanks to Internet, physicists around the world get to know of current developments through the Los Alamos-based e-print repository and soon biomedical researchers will have their own e-print repository. The printed journal has virtually lost its position of pre-eminence. By 2010, the internet is expected to surpass the combined impact of the television, telephone and personal computer.

This Almanac, claiming to be the complete guide to the ever-changing internet industry, attempts to tell you all about the people and organizations of this

BOOK REVIEWS

rapidly growing industry. It draws much of the information presented from well-known sources such as Upside, Forrester Research, Relevant Knowledge, and International Data Corp. The authors have acknowledged 37 such sources.

After a brief overview of the internet and intranet, the authors talk about internet companies and internet people and list about 1,500 companies and well over 4,000 people. There are tables listing companies on the basis of financial indicators such as revenue, revenue growth, return to shareholders and market capitalization. Netscape, Microsoft and Sun are listed as the influential companies and IBM Internet Connection is rated as the best ISP and America Online the

worst. There are also lists of companies making effective use of the internet and intranet technologies and America's most wired cities and towns. Entries on people include company affiliations, URLs of web sites, email addresses and telephone numbers. There are three lists of the 100 most influential internet people. Bill Gates is in all the three, but Andy Grove is on only two of them. A whole chapter is devoted to employment information and salary and wealth trends.

Internet conferences, publications, publishing companies and often-visited websites are listed and a section is devoted to internet history and another for market forecasts. Statistics on the use of internet in different countries is provided in the

form of simple time-series tables. In the year 2000, it is estimated that there will be 0.44 internet host computers per 1,000 people in India and 1.55 internet users for every 1,000 Indians. The statistics on India is not part of the last chapter on internet humour.

This directory may find many buyers in the United States. There may not be (m)any in India.

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MEETINGS/SYMPOSIA/SEMINARS

5th World Conference on Injury Prevention and Control

Date: 5-8 March 2000
Place: New Delhi

Anyone working in the area of injury prevention and safety promotion will find a place at the conference. The broad areas that will get prominence are: Transportation injury; Work place injury; Sport and leisure injury; Domestic injuries; International injuries – violence and suicide; Emergency and pre-hospital care.

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International Conference of 'Geoinformatics for Natural Resource Assessment, Monitoring and Management'

Date: 9-11 March 1999
Place: Dehra Dun

The conference aims to highlight various aspects of Geoinformatics dealing with Remote Sensing, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Natural Resource Management.

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Ninth User Interaction Workshop

Date: 16-17 March 1999
Place: Hyderabad

Data product sales from National Remote Sensing Agency (NRSA) is handled by the NRSA Data Centre (NDC), which serves as an interface between the organization and its several hundred clients. NRSA has been providing satellite images to the remote sensing community in India and its neighbouring countries since 1979. The objectives of the workshop are: (i) to update users with information regarding new missions, data products, ordering procedure, data utility, user services, application, etc. and (ii) to obtain user feedback on products and NDC services.

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